

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIALECTICAL RELATIONSHIP OF THE ELEMENT OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT WITH OTHER ELEMENTS OF THE TRAINING SYSTEM

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Abstract

In the article, it is emphasized that the study of the essence and main features of the process of education implementation based on the "system-structure" approach is one of the ways to ensure its effective management. It is stated that this approach is of special importance in terms of the teacher's honest knowledge of the tasks set before the general education (the expected general results), and the regulation of the activity of the student and himself. "The "system-structure" approach opens up wide opportunities to appropriately adjust the dialectic of subsystems, components and elements contained in the process of educational implementation, which ensures that the real process exists according to the "opportunity-movement and new quality" paradigm, and avoids mistakes in the management process. The dialectic in question is controlled by the teacher thanks to the assessment.

In the research work: goals related to the implementation of formative assessment are formulated; features of formative assessment are disclosed; attention is focused on what questions formative assessment answers in the learning process; the dialectical relationship of the formative evaluation element with other elements of the training system is clarified.

Keywords: curriculum, dialectical relationship, system, element, training system, creative personality, learning strategies, assessment criteria, in-school assessment, formative assessment, self-evaluation.

Relevance of the research topic. The formation of the educational space in accordance with the challenges of the IV industrial revolution has made it necessary to improve the training, which is a way of implementing education, from both the content and procedural aspects. From the analysis and summarization of the materials obtained from scientific sources, it is concluded that the mentioned necessity is understood by both theorists and practitioners engaged in the implementation of training, and optimal options for solving the problem of improving the training process are sought. There is such a characteristic feature that draws attention to the mentioned research (search) process: the improvement of the training process is not treated as an organized system (complete), but the function of any (one or another) aspect of it - subsystem, component, element ("enabling"- function that serves to produce a new quality by turning the possibility into action) is selected as a point of view. This prevents finding the perfect option in terms of the efficiency of the educational implementation process. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to approach the training process as a "system (complete)" and to adjust the existing dialectic between its subsystems (or components, elements) [10; 8] and to perfect the system containing these subsystems (or components, elements). We believe that such a system will be formed according to the paradigm of "the learner's ability - cognition, feeling, psychomotor movement - the new quality of the learner". Despite the above, we consider the research on "Dialectical relationship of the formative evaluation

element with other elements of the training system" relevant.

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research. Education is a system based on the realities of the changing world, and one of its main goals is to create favorable conditions for the discovery and development of the student's creative abilities. [12; 34-39] Since the main value in our time, formed according to the demands of the IV industrial revolution, is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the students. This, in turn, is based on the following activity, understanding needs and abilities: 1) logical thinking; 2) critical approach to objects and events of the surrounding world; 3) independent decision-making; 4) creatively change the surroundings; 5) independent acquisition of knowledge; 6) solving practical problems; 7) setting new goals for personality development. [4; 48-49]

The skills of a student who has completed his general education are formed as general learning results, synthesis and dialectical unification of the results targeted in the teaching process of all subjects taught in general education schools.

It is undeniable that it is of particular importance for the subject teacher to honestly know the tasks set before the general education (general expected results). However, this is one side of the issue and it is necessary to systematize the activity related to the educational process with a result-oriented goal. Because the goal is

the system-creating component of the activity. In addition, it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on what strategy, based on what assessment mechanisms, so that the goal becomes action. The new necessary minimum of education at the levels of general education, the level of knowledge, the general learning outcomes of the subject and the connection of the skills to be acquired with the learning outcomes that will be achieved at individual levels of general education are considered to be one of the most important problems of education. The teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he is using in the process of which he is the facilitator and what are the specific features of this model. What superior merits of other (especially traditional) models has this model incorporated (it should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such a denial can bring more harm than good!) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process.

Referring to the research materials we have collected and our experience, we have come to the conclusion that the main features of the Education program (curriculum), which is currently applied in general education schools "...perceived as a conceptual document that enables the effective organization, purposeful and consistent implementation of all activities related to the educational process" It is in the general interest to give an interpretation based on a "system-structure" approach. [1; 140-141] It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationships between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their mutual influence, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole, the whole (organized system) formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of that system. Each system has its own structure and

the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity. [7; 104-107]

The teacher is one of the subjects of the "enabling function" in the implementation of the Education program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important for the teacher to refer to the "system-structural approach" both in his knowledge of the essence of the program and in his practical activities related to its implementation. The educational program (curriculum) includes the content, strategies, determines evaluation mechanisms. [3; 11] It is a system with special subsystems that exist in a dialectical relationship. The educational program includes the curriculum, educational programs for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies. [4; 56]

Teaching programs for each subject, which has its own place in the educational program, is a system that combines elements of three blocks (content of the subject, learning strategies, assessment of student achievements). Subject curricula: take a balanced and comprehensive approach to learning different skills; enables achievement of content standards using active learning methods; implies constant assessment of students' knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; ensures involvement of students in training, preparation and motivation for continuous education; it envisages the use of modern technologies when students are studying, evaluating their knowledge, and increasing their literacy; has adequate training resources and administrative support. [5;37] The regulated dialectic between the content of the subject, teaching strategies, student achievement assessment elements (the number of the mentioned elements is twelve and covered in three blocks) determines the efficiency of the educational system, which is an important condition for the appropriate adjustment of the dialectic between the mentioned elements, the subject of the regulation process correctly understands the nature of these elements is to do.

The block diagram form of the subject curriculum structure can be drawn as follows [5; 38]:

Summing up, it can be said that the subject curriculum is a set of documents that reflect all the activities aimed at achieving the general learning results by determining the main goals of education in general education schools and are directed to the capabilities and needs of each student. It is intended for teachers, school leaders, textbook authors, parents and the general public. The subject curriculum is the basis of the rules to be prepared in the form of appropriate instructions for the preparation of textbooks and teaching aids, planning of teaching materials, determination of teaching methods and implementation of teacher training. [6; 63] The curriculum is developed on the basis of result-oriented content standards and involves regular assessment of progress in student achievement to ensure mastery of the standards, and while setting content standards, the main goal is to gradually increase the speed of progress in student achievement, and it prioritizes instilling the necessary skills needed in daily life to students. [1; 13]

As it was emphasized above, the inter-element dialectic contained in the presented blocks conditions the cognitive, emotional-emotional and psychomotor movement of students in the learning process, the paradigm "opportunity - movement - new quality" exists and is realized. The dialectic in question is controlled by the teacher thanks to the assessment. Proper assessment is one of the key elements of effective teaching and learning. If assessment guides students in their performance, sets clear standards for learning, monitors student progress, and adjusts instruction to meet student needs, then it has a positive impact on student achievement. Evaluation enables the teacher to analyze the effectiveness of his activity, plan his future activities, monitor the development and learning achievements of students, determine how far the student has reached the set learning outcomes, and plan his activities.

Evaluation is one of the main psychological problems of group life. It is a well-known fact that the emo-

tional or intellectual, moral or aesthetic values that people give to each other play an important role not only in the formation of personality in the process of activity and communication, but also in interpersonal relations. [2;153] Pedagogical assessment appears as a special type of assessment. It has been proven many years ago that the price is of great importance as an educational tool. It has been determined that the grade has a profound effect not only on the student's intellectual work, but also on the affective-will field through the feelings of success and failure experienced by him, on the formation of the level of claims, intentions and attitudes. [11; 221-226]

Our conclusion is that there is no need to look for additional arguments to justify the necessity of applying assessment mechanisms in the teaching of any subject. It is undeniable that the main goal in determining content standards for subjects is to set goals for the mastery of those standards by each student. In order to achieve knowledge and skills according to the accepted standards, the activity of each student should be continuously stimulated, and the necessary conditions should be created for them to master higher-level standards. Ideally, no student should be allowed to fall behind throughout the school year, but instead, each student's progress should be the focus. In this regard, the assessment of student achievement is a continuous, dynamic and, in many cases, informal process. In this process, teachers' observation of students, students' performance of class work and homework, written and oral answers are equally important in terms of importance.

The results of a properly conducted assessment allow making decisions about the teacher's activity, how well this activity meets the needs of students, as well as the need to make appropriate changes in the curriculum, planning and textbooks. Assessment of student achievements is considered as the process of collecting information about the student's ability to acquire knowledge, use it, and draw conclusions, and serves the

following purposes: 1) tracking (monitoring) the student's progress (regression); 2) making decisions in the training process; 3) evaluation of student's learning results; 4) curriculum evaluation. [5; 225]

Assessment and learning processes are seen as two interrelated aspects of education. Evaluation, which is a systematic process, is built as a means of effective feedback between training results and stakeholders by including the following components: 1) evaluation data; 2) data collection; 3) assessment results; 4) assessment standards. [5; 225-226]

The factors that necessitate the creation of a new evaluation system are: 1. Determination of the efficiency level of educational activity; 2. Monitoring compliance of education standards with demand; 3. Obtaining objective information about the achievements of students across the country; 4. Improving and improving the quality of the training process. [9; 293-300]

The modern evaluation policy can be interpreted as follows: 1. Evaluation is aimed at improving the quality of education and appears as an important factor that controls it; 2. Eliminating the current assessment ensures the overall mastery of the content standards and the objectivity of the assessment; 3. It is applied at all

stages of the educational process; 4. Student's achievement (acquired values) is assessed, development is systematically monitored; 5. Evaluation standards have been defined to measure the level of mastery of content standards.

The following can be attributed to the principles to be observed in conducting the assessment: 1) suitability for the purpose; 2) mutual assessment of achievements and educational opportunities; 3) ensuring the qualitative relevance and reliability of the collected data; 4) transparency, fairness, mutual agreement and cooperation in evaluation; 5) ensuring the developmental role of assessment results in training activities.

Assessment in our country is carried out in the following directions: international assessment; national assessment; in-school assessment.

National and international evaluations are evaluation studies conducted to determine perspectives in education and are carried out by special institutions. In-school assessment is a formal assessment and serves to move students from grade to grade, from one educational level to another.

The description of the "system-structure" interpretation of the evaluation system can be presented as follows: [5; 227]

We consider it acceptable to present the comparison of modern assessment with traditional assessment in the form of a table as follows:

Traditional assessment	Modern assessment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - During the evaluation, it was considered as giving a grade to the student; the student studied only for the sake of getting a grade. - Current evaluation led to formalism; it was based on the teacher's subjective opinion. - It was applied only in a certain part of the educational process. - Basically, the level of knowledge was assessed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluation is aimed at improving the quality of education and appears as an important factor that controls it. - Eliminating current assessment ensures full mastery of content standards and objectivity of assessment. - It is applied at all stages of the educational process. - The student's achievement (acquired values) is evaluated, his development is systematically monitored. - Assessment standards are defined to measure the level of mastery of content standards.

The following is the interpretation of the evaluation by components in tabular form can be presented as: [13; 19]

Components	Traditional assessment	Modern assessment
Objectives	It was considered focused on the development of knowledge, skills, and habits; In reality, the level of knowledge was mainly assessed.	It is aimed at the development of knowledge, skills, habits, values, personality; the student's achievement (gained values) is evaluated, his development is systematically monitored.
Roles and responsibilities	Assessment was seen as giving a grade to the student; the student studied only to get a grade; it was applied only in a certain part of the educational process.	Assessment is aimed at improving the quality of education and appears as an important factor controlling it, it is applied at all stages of the educational process.
Types and directions	In-school current and final assessment	International, national, intra-school assessment; Diagnostic, formative, summative assessment
Features	It was more formal, imprecise, based on the teacher's subjective opinion, and unsystematic.	It is based on the standard. It is more objective, accurate, and adequately systematic.
Criteria, indicators	It is a subject-based achievement assessment. More quantitative indicators are considered.	Based on assessment standards. Quality indicators are taken into account.
Methods and tools	Limited and inflexible (oral response, tests, tests)	More diverse and flexible (interview, conversation, observation, rubrics, tasks, cooperation with parents and other subject teachers, oral responses of students, analysis of students' writing, test results).
Forms	Intra-class, intra-school	Intra-classroom, intra-school, centralized.

Various assessment methods and tools are used for data collection. Assessment methods are procedures used to collect information about students' learning activities. Assessment tools are the tools used to implement that method. Depending on the type of evaluation, methods and tools are different. For example, if the teacher's goal during formative assessment is to check

the student's ability to solve mathematical problems, the method he will use is assignment, and the assessment tool is mathematical studies.

In order to clarify our opinion, let's present information about the methods and tools used in formative assessment in the form of a table:

Methods	Means
Oral and written presentation	Observation sheets, self-assessment sheet
Research project	Criteria table
rubric (schema)	Criteria rating scale
Test	Test tasks
Self assessment	Self-assessment sheets
Games	Observation sheets

By the way, let's note that although test tasks are currently gaining popularity as an assessment tool, the teacher teaching the subject should not be addicted to test tasks in diagnostic, formative and even summative

assessment. Among the methods that develop the oral and written speech skills, logical thinking, and independent thinking of the teaching students are the project

(assessment tool - the students' presentation and the criteria table drawn up by the teacher), the oral survey (the assessment tool - the registration sheet for oral speech skills), test writing tasks (problem and example solution) should be widely used. It is recommended to use test tasks not continuously, but whenever possible, and without hesitation in summative assessment.

According to our understanding, the main essence of in-school assessment is formative assessment.

Formative assessment is the constant monitoring of the student's learning activities and the assessment of the level of focus on knowledge and skills arising from the content standards determined for any stage of the process. Formative evaluation is carried out in order to monitor the progress and setbacks of the student towards the realization of the accepted standards, to eliminate the problems encountered at this time and to guide the student. Formative assessment is a process that leads the student forward and helps him to achieve the set goal by forming the basis of the learning process. Formative assessment is a process that accompanies the lesson.

The goals related to the implementation of the formative assessment can be formulated as follows: 1. To achieve the student's learning results by shaping the student's knowledge and skills; 2. Learning the training needs of students; 3. To ensure the monitoring of students' progress in the field of training; 4. Investigate the reasons for the student's failure to succeed and ensure his development; 5. Monitor students' acquisition of the basic knowledge and skills expected in the content standards for each subject; 6. To develop students' self-assessment skills; 7. To ensure the correct orientation and efficiency of the educational process. [5; 230]

Formative assessment answers these questions: 1. What is the student's goal, that is, what will the student learn? 2. What is the student's current situation, that is, how much does he know about the issue he needs to study at the moment? 3. How can the student reach his goal, that is, what should he do to reach the goal? [8; 104]

In scientific sources (see: [8]), the characteristics of formative assessment are attributed to: 1. Compliance with learning outcomes. As is well known, learning outcomes are predetermined, helping to determine what students should learn, be able to do, and based on which criteria will be evaluated. Determining the learning results before the lesson and announcing them to the students makes the activity goal-oriented, helps to determine the evaluation criteria and evaluate the learning activity. Also, a well-defined learning outcome ensures the application and integration of knowledge. It should also be emphasized that when the training result is aimed at the formation of skills, the goal is not only the acquisition of knowledge, but also the application of knowledge in different contexts. Learning outcomes are at the heart of the learning, teaching and assessment process. A well-formed learning outcome should reflect how students will apply the new knowledge and skills they have acquired, rather than repeating information. What is meant by "Compliance with learning outcomes", which is considered as one of the characteristics of formative assessment and is considered as the

principle of implementation of the assessment, is that the assessment conducted with this principle can easily show to what extent the students have reached the learning outcomes. [8; 56]

2. Having evaluation criteria. It is known that assessment criteria are special standards or guidelines used to create a clear idea of what is expected of students during the activity, and how knowledge and skills will be assessed. When developing evaluation criteria, its following features should be taken into account: 1) the principle of compatibility should be expected; 2) must be clear and specific; 3) it should be measurable, allowing for objective assessment; 4) must ensure conducting an effective evaluation process. [8; 58]

By the way, let's also emphasize that the criteria should be shared with the students at the beginning of the learning project.

3. Effective feedback. It is undeniable that the main factor determining the success of "teacher-student" communication is the establishment of effective feedback with students, i.e. giving feedback. Feedback is information given to the student about the progress of the work done and the mistakes made to achieve the goal. In other words, feedback (giving feedback) is a two-way exchange of information between a teacher and a student, and between students and students. The feedback given should be future-oriented, including what to do and how to do it, not the past.

Each feedback provided serves a purpose and is useful to the learner only when appropriate. By purpose, feedback is formative and summative. Formative feedback is provided during the learning process. Its main purpose is to develop the student, to guide his activities correctly, to develop the student until summative assessment. Feedback has different purposes and content.

According to the purpose of feedback, there are the following types: 1) corrective feedback; 2) descriptive feedback; 3) constructive feedback; 4) motivational feedback.

Scientific sources give comments on the concept of "feedback content" and refer to this concept: 1) feedback about the learning process; 2) feedback about the content of the subject; 3) feedback about the result. [8; 58]

It should be noted that feedback can be conducted both among students themselves and between teachers and students. Also, the student himself can provide feedback on his activity. The main thing is that the feedback given is objective. For this, it is important to form critical and creative thinking, metacognitive skills in the student, and develop his emotional intelligence. Feedback affects not only the student's academic performance, but also his behavior, social skills, communication, etc. should be attributed. Another important factor in giving feedback is that the feedback is focused on the student's cognitive activity rather than their emotions. The features that make feedback effective are grouped as follows: 1. To be as specific as possible (to convey information about the student to him not in general, but in specific aspects); 2. Is to provide feedback as timely as possible; 3. To evaluate student achievement in terms of learning objectives; 4. It is to convey

feedback to students sensitively (the following expressions can be used during feedback: I like that you work tirelessly on tasks; I see that you used this method in solving the task; I am interested, what is the reason for using this method at this point?; If for this task If you didn't use another method, would the result be what you expected? etc.).

Every teacher should provide positive, supportive, constructive, and student-centered feedback to a student. Feedback is not given only by the teacher, students can also give feedback to each other. For this, they should be able to give feedback that is constructive, i.e. focused on each other's development, emotionally sensitive and more focused on positive aspects.

4. Continuous monitoring. It is known that the observation process is an integral part of all processes in the classroom, including assessment. Observation has a special role in formative assessment, because it is at this time that it is possible to measure students' understanding, to evaluate their learning needs, their activities and to develop them. In order to effectively conduct observation in formative assessment, it is necessary to focus on a number of points. Observation in formative assessment: is a continuous and continuous process; can be conducted formally and informally; useful for effective feedback; serves to collect information about the student's learning needs; increases the possibility of understanding the dynamics of the class; makes it possible to "read" non-verbal information (students' body language, facial expressions and other non-verbal signals provide information about their emotional state and understanding of the subject); serves to support self-evaluation. [8; 105]

It should be emphasized that in general, observation during formative assessment serves to create a student-oriented, supportive environment in the classroom. It also enables the teacher to adapt his methodology and strategies to the needs of his students.

Student self-assessment and peer assessment are an important part of formative assessment. The teacher is not the only person doing the assessment in the classroom. Students can monitor and measure their own learning. Student self-evaluation is an important aspect of learning because students can achieve their learning goals (learning outcomes) when they understand these goals and what they need to achieve them. In self-assessment, the learner uses metacognitive thinking on the one hand to measure his own learning and check where he is on the way to achieving learning goals, and on the other hand, he thinks about learning strategies for himself and how to apply them. If students have metacognitive knowledge, they can determine a more suitable strategy for a certain learning activity.

To summarize what has been said, let us emphasize that in self-assessment, the student performs two activities: he measures his own learning and determines a learning strategy for his development. During self-assessment, students are in a kind of internal dialogue with themselves. The important issue here is the constant support of teachers for the formation of students' inner voices, that is, their self-reflection.

Like self-assessment, peer assessment is one of the main tools of student-centred assessment. Peer assessment is when students give feedback to other students and the goal is for students to help each other in the learning process. The importance of this kind of assessment is great in education because the student who gives feedback on his/her activity benefits from this process as well as the student who receives feedback about his/her performance, because while giving feedback, students understand and master the learning standards and criteria, which allows them to evaluate their own activities as well. In this respect, peer evaluation and self-evaluation are closely related. Peer assessment requires a strong supportive environment in the classroom so that students trust each other and feedback does not undermine interpersonal relationships. In a classroom with this kind of cultural learning environment, students understand that they are not only responsible for their own learning, but also for the learning of their peers, and part of that responsibility is to provide respectful, constructive, and nonjudgmental feedback.

Formative assessment can be both student and parent focused. Depending on this, the results of the formative assessment are delivered in different forms:

- Constructive comments (notes) are written in the student's notebook or other worksheets and concrete instructions and tasks are given to improve the results;
- Student feedback can be created using various qualitative methods of formative assessment;
- The parent's attention is brought to the attention of the student through the school book, to what extent his child has progressed according to the content standards or the current learning outcomes or what results he has achieved;
- The teacher records the results of the formative assessment in the "Teacher's formative assessment book".

An evaluation table with specific criteria and serving as a guide is provided for evaluation. The main purpose of rubrics is to evaluate and develop student activity. These criteria typically describe the quality of student performance across levels. The rubric consists of three main parts: 1) criteria; 2) quality level; 3) description of quality levels corresponding to the criterion. A rubric is one of the most useful forms of formative assessment. It can also be used in diagnostic and summative assessment.

Rubrics have advantages. These are the following:

1. Rubrics make assessment more fair, objective, reliable and consistent.
2. To prepare the rubrics, the teacher defines his own criteria for the relevant conditions and thereby better describes the learning objectives.
3. Rubrics provide the teacher with useful information about the effectiveness of teaching.
4. Rubrics facilitate assessment in telerogenic classrooms through a range of grade levels. [5; 233-237]

Rubrics are divided into 2 types according to their design: analytical and holistic rubric.

Comparison of holistic and analytical rubrics:

1. Holistic assessment describes the overall picture of student achievement. Analytical evaluation determines the marks of the student in separate fields of activity, and gives more detailed information about the achievements of the students by consistently evaluating their activities.

2. Holistic assessment is quick while analytical assessment takes more time.

Holistic rubric. As mentioned, the holistic rubric provides an overall impression of the student's work and is often based on a 4-6 point scale that reflects performance levels.

Advantages: quick assessment, provides an overview of student achievement.

Weaknesses: does not provide detailed information, it may be difficult to give an overall assessment.

It is advisable to use holistic rubrics in the following cases:

1. When you want to get an instant picture of achievement;

2. If a single aspect is adequate to determine quality.

Analytical rubric. Analytical rubric, as mentioned, assigns separate grades for multifaceted aspects of the student's work (activity). A scale of 4-6 points is used to evaluate each aspect.

Advantages: provides more detailed information, more consistent assessment for each student, class and year.

Weaknesses: takes a lot of time to evaluate (time consuming).

It is recommended to use the analytical rubric in the following cases: a) When you want to see the relative advantage and weakness; b) When you want to get detailed information (feedback); c) When you want to evaluate complex activity or result; ç) When asking students to evaluate their own understanding or performance.

The following are recommended for rubric-based assessment: 1) Determine the learning objective (knowledge, skills, attitudes, etc.). Think about what you want students to know and be able to do; 2) Select the purpose of assessment (diagnostic, formative, summative); 3) Decide what type of rubric to use (holistic, analytical); 4) Identify the aspects (criteria) that are interesting to you and describe these aspects; 5) Determine how to express different levels of achievement; 6) Specify the number of achievement levels (or evaluation points); 7) Express level descriptors; 8) Write a verbal description of all achievement level descriptors;

The result. 1. The content, strategies, and assessment mechanisms of the training system (educational implementation process) built according to the curriculum model are its subsystems; these subsystems depend on the emergent nature of the system they contain, and exist in a dialectical relationship among themselves; the

mentioned dialectic conditions the paradigm "possibility - movement - new quality";

2. Formative assessment is a way of constantly monitoring the student's learning activities and determining the level of knowledge and skills arising from the content standards determined for any stage of the process; assessment;

3. Formative assessment helps the educator to determine options for overcoming the problems encountered during the student's progress towards the realization of the accepted standards from a theoretical and technological point of view;

4. Formative assessment is a process that leads the student forward and helps him to achieve the set goal by forming the basis of the learning process;

5. The "system-structure" approach performs the function of the regulator of the process of appropriate placement of teaching units, elements contained in teaching units, as components of a perfect system in the student's experience from the results of the assessment.

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